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Enhancing Safety and Efficiency for Vulnerable Road Users: Design and Evaluation of a Mobile User Interface for Cooperative Maneuver Coordination

for the award of the academic degree

Bachelor of Science (B. Sc.)

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Declaration under Oath

I hereby declare in lieu of an oath that I have written this bachelor's thesis independently and without the use of any sources other than those indicated. Any ideas taken directly or indirectly from external sources are identified as such.

The thesis has not yet been submitted in the same or a similar form to any other examination authority and has not yet been published.

Ulm, 14.03.2025

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Foreword

	<p>This Bachelor Thesis is part of the PoDIUM project that has received funding under grant agreement No. 101069547. It is co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</p>	
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Abstract

This thesis explores the design and evaluation of a user interface (UI) for vulnerable road users (VRU) interacting with maneuver coordination messages (MCM) in urban environments within the scope of the PoDIUM project. The primary objective is to enhance the safety and efficiency of VRUs, specifically bicyclists, by developing a mobile interface on an Android smartphone to facilitate effective communication with a multi-access edge computing (MEC) server. The thesis employs a streamlined version of the “goal-directed design process”, incorporating best practices and insights from existing literature on UI design and human-machine interaction (HMI). The resulting UI is then evaluated using the GOMS framework and design grid methodology and compared with the old UI concept of the PoDIUM project. The findings demonstrate significant improvements in task efficiency, visual layout, and user experience. The newly developed UI reduces the number of interactions required, simplifies the visual design, and enhances safety by minimizing distractions. The thesis concludes with recommendations for further refinement and validation methods to ensure that the UI meets the evolving needs of VRUs in dynamic traffic environments, contributing to the broader goal of achieving safer roads in line with the European Union’s “Vision Zero” initiative.

Keywords

User Interface (UI), Vulnerable Road Users (VRU), Android Application, Mobile Phone, Bicyclist, Maneuver Coordination Messages (MCM), Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), Road Safety, PoDIUM Project, Vision Zero, GOMS

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List of Abbreviation

EU	European Union
CCAM	Cooperative, connected, and automated mobility
MEC	Multi-access edge computing
VRU	Vulnerable road user
CAV	Connected and automated vehicle
ITS	Intelligent transport systems
VAM	VRU awareness message
MCM	Maneuver coordination message
UI	User interface
HMI	Human-machine interaction
ITS-S	ITS station
CPM	Collective perception messages
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
sp	Scale-independent pixels
GOMS	Goals, operators, methods, and selection rules

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

In 2022, the number of road fatalities on European roads was reported to be 20,634 [4], with 38% (7,880) of these occurring on urban roads [5]. This represents a significant decrease of 22% in fatal road accidents since 2012 [4]. Despite this progress, the European Union (EU) set the ambitious goal known as “Vision Zero”, which aims to eliminate all fatalities and serious injuries on European roads by 2050 [6]. To contribute to this goal, the EU is co-funding the PoDIUM Project through its “Horizon Europe” program [7], an initiative aimed at advancing cooperative, connected, and automated mobility (CCAM) technologies in Europe [2]. The PoDIUM project’s primary objective is to demonstrate and validate the benefits and applicability of CCAM in real-world traffic conditions through comprehensive testing and development activities [2].

This bachelor’s thesis is conducted as part of the PoDIUM project, specifically use case 1 “cooperative corridor management in city of Ulm” focusing on utilizing a cooperative local environment model to manage complex urban traffic situations, thereby improving safety and efficiency [2]. Use case 1 explores two related scenarios [2]. This thesis will primarily focus on scenario 2, which involves a multi-access edge computing (MEC) server, a connected vulnerable road user VRU, a connected and automated vehicle CAV, and an arbitrary number of infrastructure sensors interconnected through various communication technologies [2].

1.2 Problem statement

In Scenario 2, all participants are connected to the MEC server with the VRU and CAV providing their route, position, and velocity information [2]. The server generates “digital twins” and shares them with the connected road users [2]. As the VRU approaches a road blockage, they send out a request to handle the situation and cooperate with the other users [2]. The MEC server plans a cooperative maneuver to safely navigate the VRU in a reserved corridor around the obstacle. After the navigation, the road users can resume their journey normally [2]. Throughout this process, the “digital twin” is continuously updated with new data to reflect the current state of the environment [2].

The VRU in this scenario will be represented by a bicyclist connected via an Android smartphone supporting 5G cm-Wave technology, which is mounted on the vehicle [2]. By periodically sending intelligent transport systems (ITS) VRU awareness messages (VAM) between 1-10Hz to the

server, the MEC server can create the “digital twin” and calculate a possible maneuver [2]. Primary communication regarding cooperative maneuver information will be done via the ITS maneuver coordination messages (MCM), which the bicyclist needs to send and receive [2].

To interactively communicate with the MEC server, the Android phone’s software requires a specifically developed user interface (UI) in order to complete cooperative driving maneuvers [2]. Distracted driving, especially cell phone use, poses a significant risk factor for bicyclist safety during overtaking maneuvers [8]. Therefore, a potential UI must enable the user to efficiently communicate with the MEC server, convey maneuver information to the user, and prioritize their safety.

1.3 Research question

How can a mobile UI be designed for VRUs to effectively receive, process, and respond to MCMs from a MEC server, enabling their participation in cooperative traffic scenarios while maintaining safety and user experience?

1.4 Objectives

1.4.1 Analyze the state of the art

By conducting a comprehensive review of the current literature and technologies related to UI design and human-machine interaction (HMI) for road users, this thesis will establish a robust baseline of scientifically proven best practices. The analysis will focus on identifying the latest advancements and best practices in the field, particularly those relevant to VRUs such as cyclists. Additionally, various design principles will be examined with the goal of identifying effective and proven design guidelines by experts, and synthesizing those applicable to the use case of this thesis.

1.4.2 Develop and refine a user interface prototype

The next objective is to analyze the requirements of VRU interaction with MCMs, as well as the goals of the user. Based on these requirements, goals, and identified best practices, a prototype UI will be developed and refined according to established design guidelines.

1.4.3 Evaluate the user interface prototype

The third objective is to confirm the effectiveness of the developed prototype by evaluating it using different proven evaluation methods. This will involve systematic testing and analysis to determine how well the prototype performs in terms of usability, efficiency, and visual appeal. The evaluation will compare the new UI with the old baseline UI to measure improvements in task efficiency and visual layout.

1.4.4 Analyze evaluation data and make final recommendations

The final objective is to analyze the evaluation data to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the prototype. Based on these insights, final recommendations will be made to enhance the design and functionality of the mobile UI for VRUs. These recommendations will aim to improve the overall user experience and to ensure the UI effectively supports the needs of VRUs in dynamic traffic environments.

1.5 Definitions

In order to provide clarity and ensure a common understanding of key terms used throughout this thesis, this section defines the specific terminology and concepts that are fundamental to the study. By clearly outlining these definitions, readers will be better equipped to comprehend the context and nuances of the research.

1.5.1 User interface (UI)

A UI is the medium through which users interact with a digital device or software application. It includes all visual and interactive elements such as screens, buttons, icons, and menus that facilitate user interaction. According to Cooper et al. (2014), UI design encompasses not only the layout of widgets on a screen but also the broader discipline of interaction design, which involves designing the behavior of complex interactive systems [9].

Interaction design focuses on creating interfaces that are intuitive, efficient, and responsive to user inputs, ensuring that form, function, content, and behavior are seamlessly integrated [9]. This approach goes beyond static form design, addressing the dynamic and evolving nature of user interactions with digital products [9]. The primary objective of UI and interaction design is to create user experiences that are both effective and satisfying, by carefully considering how users will interact with the product and ensuring that the design supports their needs and goals [9].

1.5.2 Vulnerable road user (VRU)

The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (2022) describes VRUs as road users who are particularly vulnerable to collisions with other road users [10]. They classify VRUs in four different profiles based on their behavior [11]. From now on, when referring to VRUs in this bachelor's thesis, profile 2 is meant, which includes bicyclists.

Furthermore, a VRU is considered to be a living being which participates in the road traffic [11]. Therefore, a bicycle by itself is not a VRU; it becomes a VRU only in combination with a human being riding it [11].

1.5.3 Vulnerable road user awareness messages (VAM)

VAMs are messages transmitted from VRU ITS station (ITS-S), which in this thesis refers to an Android smartphone, to create and maintain awareness of the originating VRU [12]. A VAM contains the originating VRUs status and attribute information [12]. When a VAM is received by another ITS-S (in case of this thesis the MEC server), it becomes aware of the presence, position, motion state, and desired path of the originating VRU [12].

In the use case of this thesis, the VRU ITS-S periodically creates and sends VAMs at a frequency of 1-10Hz to the connected MEC server [2]. This information is then fused with the local infrastructure sensor data to create a "digital twin" [2]. The "digital twin" is used to calculate potential collisions, plan coordination efforts, and inform other road users of all participants [2].

1.5.4 Multi-access edge computing (MEC)

The MEC server processes all the information from the connected infrastructure sensors and the data from the connected road users, integrating all of this into a global environmental model known as the "digital twin" [2]. The "digital twin" is then used to update the road users about each other's presence, via collective perception messages (CPM), and efficiently plan the execution of cooperative driving maneuvers [2].

1.5.5 Maneuver coordination messages (MCM)

In order to participate in cooperative traffic scenarios, the VRU must be able to interact bidirectionally with the MEC server. [2] This is achieved with MCMs, which are messages to coordinate connected vehicles and other road users efficiently through traffic [1].

At the time of the writing of this thesis, the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) has not yet defined an official standard, still being in the pre-standardization phase [13]. That is why the PoDIUM project has its own MCM definition, which is based on a draft by the ETSI [2]. This definition also covers urban scenarios and mixed traffic of automated and manually driven vehicles, which according to Mertens et al. (2021), most proposed MCM formats at the time don't include [1].

Mertens et al. (2021) propose a MCM that consists of two primary containers: the "VehicleManeuverContainer", which details the vehicle's current maneuver, and the "SuggestedManeuverContainer", which specifies the suggested maneuver for the receiving vehicle [1]. This structure is illustrated in figure 1, which shows the proposed MCM format by Mertens et al. (2021).

Maneuver-CoordinationMessage	ItsPduHeader			
	Maneuver-Coordination	GenerationDeltaTime		
		MCMParameters	BasicContainer (reference position, station type)	
			Maneuver-Container = CHOICE [...]	VehicleManeuverContainer (trajectory, route, advice response, ...)
		SuggestedManeuverContainer (ID, corridor, longitudinal waypoints, ...)		
VehicleManeuver-Container	VehicleState (type, speed, yaw angle)			
	Planned-Trajectory	StartDeltaTime, DeltaTime		
		List of TrajectoryPoint	XDistance, YDistance, Speed, YawAngle	
	Desired-Route	List of Waypoint	XDistance, YDistance	
	Advice-Response	ManeuverID, AdviceUpdateID		
AdviceFollowed (accept, reject, pending)				
SuggestedManeuverContainer	ManeuverID, AdviceUpdateID, TargetStationID			
	ParticipatingRoadUserIDs			
	ConfirmationRequiredFlag			
	ManeuverParameters = CHOICE [...]	SuggestedManeuver	List of Longitudinal-Maneuver-Waypoint	Waypoint (XDistance, YDistance)
				MinArrivalTime, MaxArrivalTime
				MinVelocity, MaxVelocity
				MinDurationOfStop
				PrecedingRoadUserID, FollowingRoadUserID
				YieldToRoadUserIDs
	Maneuver-Corridor	Polygon: list of (XDist., YDist.)		
TerminationStatus: regular maneuver end or error				

Figure 1: Proposed ManeuverCoordinationMessage by Mertens et al. (2021) [1]

In the use case of this thesis, road users signal their willingness to cooperation by periodically sending MCMs with their “DesiredRoute”. After calculating a cooperative maneuver, the MEC

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server responds with a recommended action to the VRU via an MCM that includes the “ConfirmationRequiredFlag”. On the VRU side, these MCMs must be processed and displayed as information. The VRU needs to respond with an MCM containing the “AdviceResponse” set to either “accept”, “reject”, or “pending”. When the suggested Maneuver is accepted, the VRU and MEC server keep exchanging MCMs until either party sends an MCM with a “TerminationStatus” [1] [2].

2 Related work

2.1 Introduction

To fully understand the state of the art and learn from best and worst practices, this literature review focuses on UI design for traffic applications and HMI in dynamic environments. As Cooper (2014) emphasizes in *About Face: The Essentials of Interaction Design*, research is critical to good design [9]. Given the limited research specifically addressing UI design for VRU at the time of this thesis, this review also includes research on UI design for traffic applications in cars. The principles discussed in these studies are often applicable to the use case of this thesis. Additionally, Cooper advocates for a focus on qualitative rather than quantitative research [9], which aligns with the approach taken in this review.

2.2 Safe and efficient information presentation for road users

Traffic requires every participant to be fully aware of each other and always be cautious. Therefore, UI design for traffic applications cannot always follow the rules of regular UI design. Users can not and should not always pay full attention to the UI, as their first priority should be safe travel from point A to point B. The EU Commission has issued recommendations for safe and efficient in-vehicle information and communication systems. Although these recommendations are primarily intended for cars, some can be applied to the use case of this thesis as well.

Regarding the priority of information, safety-relevant information should have higher priority and should be accurate and timely [14].

For information presentation, the Commission recommends that visually displayed information should be quickly and easily understood with short glances [14]. Since the priority for road users is to safely maneuver through traffic situations, longer glances on the in-vehicle UI Systems would be counterproductive. This means that the UI should not be cluttered with too much information, and the information presented should be simple to understand. To achieve this, the Commission recommends the use of internationally and/or nationally agreed standards for icons, symbols, words and acronyms [14]. For example, if a user needs to stop the vehicle, the use of a “stop sign” would be most effective to communicate with the user, as this is a symbol already learned.

Lindner et al. (2022) explored an approach for automated vehicle-to-bicyclist communication through their mobile application designed to resolve interactions at intersections. Their study

utilized simplified pictorial information to convey traffic situations [15]. They further recommended incorporating dynamic elements into the UI to enhance the understanding of these situations [15]. Lindner et al. argue that dynamic elements can improve the comprehension of traffic scenarios, but they caution that a balance must be struck between detailed visualization and simple, fast comprehensibility [15]. However, it is important to note that this recommendation is intended for future revisions of their app, and their study did not empirically evaluate whether this approach is more effective for information presentation to traffic users [15]. While the study's findings showed that users trusted the application's design and reliability [15], it is important to note that the study was conducted in a simulator and not in real-world traffic. As Franz (2024) states in *Usability and UX Design*, a simulated environment can influence a study, with a poorer simulation having a stronger impact on the results [16].

A cycling warning system was developed and evaluated by Kreißig et al. (2022), using simplified pictorial information to provide users with simple and easy-to-understand warnings [17]. Their study concluded that users felt safer with the system than without it [17]. Additionally, users were asked to assess their perceived workload during the use of the app, and it was found that the system had no significant effect on perceived workload [17]. However, this study was also conducted on a bicycle simulator [17], which does not address whether these findings can be applied to real-world traffic.

Matviienko et al. (2016) explored a less distracting way to present navigation information using ambient light in a car [18]. Their study participants found the ambient light navigation to be effective and less distracting than traditional graphical UI navigation [18]. By shifting the navigation information to the periphery of human vision, the driver can maintain their focus on the road [18]. While this study was also only conducted on a driving simulator [18], its applicability to the use case of this thesis is questionable. Using ambient light on a single mobile device for bicyclists outdoors may be challenging. However, the idea of shifting some information to the periphery of the bicyclist's vision could be worth exploring.

The modality of how the system warns the user is its own focus topic of multiple studies. Strohaecker et al. (2022) compared auditory and tactile warnings against a baseline group without warnings for cyclists in a controlled test environment [19]. The reaction times of the auditory group were better, with participants reacting to all warnings, while the tactile and baseline groups missed some warnings [19]. A similar result can be seen in a study by Erdei et al. (2020), where participating cyclists rode along real traffic and received different signals - auditory, vibro-tactile, and visual - and had to push a button when they received a signal [20]. The auditory signals had the highest response rate with 97.4% followed by vibro-tactile signals

at 87.2%, and visual signals at 65.1% [20]. While visual signals had the worst performance in the study, the majority of participants (67%) later indicated a preference for visual signals when asked about their preferred modality [20]. This suggests a trust in visual information, likely because users are more accustomed to graphical UIs. The study also included environmental conditions, like visual, auditory and haptic interference, and concluded that auditory signals were the least impacted by these conditions [20]. Although the study measured the average ambient noise and frequencies on the test environment and chose signals 10 dB louder and on different frequencies, a busy street could potentially be loud enough to mask important auditory signals for the user. Additionally, both Strohhaeker et al. (2022) and Erdei et al. (2020) used an external loudspeaker with the smartphone [19][20], leaving it unclear if auditory signals could have also been perceived with only the smartphone's speakers, which is the assumption and use case for this study. Also for the vibro-tactile signals, Erdei et al. (2020) used motors at the handlebars to convey information to the user [20]. Erdei et al. (2020) acknowledged that vibro-tactile signals were sometimes hard to distinguish from the roads vibrations [20], which would make them less suitable for warning cyclists especially when there is no vibration motors at the handlebars like in this thesis' use case.

Duffner et al. (2022) investigated how additional auditory signals can improve visual navigational instructions and compared it against visual only instructions [21]. Participants cycled a predefined route with their eye movements tracked through special glasses, with fewer glances at the screen considered a better result [21]. The experiment included five different traffic scenarios, each classified as either simple or complex [21]. The study came to the conclusion that in the complex scenarios, purely visual instructions resulted in fewer display glances, while in simple scenarios, visual instructions with added auditory signals performed better [21]. However, for their auditory signals Duffner et al. (2022) used a single in-ear headphone and did not test auditory-only instructions [21]. Whether the same results could be achieved with only a smartphone's speakers remains questionable.

Wang et al. (2020) reached a similar conclusion, finding that auditory instructions work better in simpler traffic scenarios [22]. Their study also compared visual and auditory instructions in a driving simulator for cars. While auditory instructions increased reaction times, visual instructions helped users drive more accurately and efficiently [22]. Furthermore, they recommend more research into a mix of visual and auditory modalities [22]. However, since this study was also conducted in a simulator, the results may not be fully applicable to real-world traffic.

A study comparing mixed modalities, conducted by von Sawitzky et al. (2022), developed and evaluated a notification system to warn cyclists about potential dooring accidents [23]. While

the study was also only conducted in a simulator, participants preferred the signal modalities that included auditory cues over visual only messages [23], indicating that a combination of any modality with auditory signals seems to be the approach users feel the safest with.

2.3 Human-machine interaction in dynamic environments

For interaction with the UI, the driver should always be able to keep one hand on the steering wheel [14], or in our use case the bike handle. The EU Commission also advises that systems should not require long and uninterruptible sequences of user-interaction, with a short interface sequence described as less than four to five individual control input/button presses and less than two menu changes [14]. Also, every interaction needs to return some clearly perceptible feedback to the user, indicating that a change in the system has occurred as a result of their input [14]. This ensures that the system feels responsive and reliable to the user.

There are not many studies on the interaction between automated vehicles and bicyclists at the time of this thesis. Lindner (2022) conducted a study to evaluate a communication application designed to enable safe interaction between automated vehicles and VRUs such as bicyclists [15]. For their application, Lindner and his team used a mix of visual and auditory signals to convey information. The auditory signals were used to alert users about new information, ensuring that the bicyclist did not have to continuously look at the device screen, which could distract them from the surrounding traffic [15].

Orekhov et al. (2019) analyzed how users can effectively pass information to other connected drivers via a cooperative human-machine interface [24]. They tested different modalities, like direct input and voice input, with voice commands found to be more efficient and reducing cognitive load and distraction for the driver [24]. However, the results were only calculated using the goals, operators, methods, and selection rules (GOMS) method without an empirical user study [24]. While extensive theoretical and empirical research has confirmed the robustness and reliability of GOMS models, John and Kieras (1996) point out the limitations of the method and emphasize it to be viewed not as a replacement but as a way to reduce user testing [25].

2.4 Best practices for general user interface design

To approach the UI design for this thesis, examining established and proven patterns, as well as recommendations from experts in the field, is crucial. Best practices in UI design are based on extensive research and practical experience, which can provide valuable insights into creating intuitive, efficient, and user-friendly interfaces. By leveraging these best practices, the design process can be more structured and effective, ultimately leading to a better user experience.

However, not all principles can be directly applied in the context of a safety-critical mobile app for CAV to VRU cooperation. Therefore, it is important to critically consider the specific context of this thesis when evaluating and selecting these principles.

Regarding visual presentation, Rogers (2023) recommends highlighting information when it requires attention at a given stage of a task [26]. This can be achieved through the use of animated graphics, color, or underlining of typography [26]. In the context of this thesis, it would be best to minimize the use of animated graphics, as their overuse could distract the driver. Rogers also urges avoiding cluttering visual interfaces with too much information [26]. Especially, the overuse of color and graphics can be distracting or even annoying [26].

Similarly, Cooper et al. (2014) advocate for a minimalist approach, emphasizing that “less is more” in good design [9]. According to them, designers should strive to solve design problems with the fewest addition of form and behavior [9]. This is a concept not dissimilar to the principles followed by developers, who will agree that better algorithms are clearer and shorter. Cooper et al. further argue that excessive interactions can create unnecessary work for users, leading to a taxing experience [9]. Therefore, they recommend that designers minimize the effort required by users when interacting with an interface [9], which also aligns with the EU Commission’s recommendations for fewer and shorter interaction sequences.

Cooper et al. (2014) emphasize the importance of guiding users through a clear visual hierarchy [9]. Designers can achieve this by grouping related visual elements, establishing relationships between them. Subsequently, they can use position, color, and size to distinguish levels of hierarchy within these groupings [9]. For instance, increased size or brighter colors signify higher hierarchy, indicating to the user that an element is more important [9]. Furthermore, they recommend creating a logical path for eye movements through the interface, avoiding haphazard placement of elements [9].

When using imagery or icons, Tidwell et al. (2019) recommend looking at UI conventions seen on the web or from other icons [27]. They argue that using common conventions found in other designs make it easier for the user to understand without the need to relearn what an icon means [27]. Additionally, they recommend that all icons should share the same visual style and warn not to rely on icons alone, recommending the use of additional text for maximum user comprehension [27].

Another critical component is text and typography. Cooper et al. (2014) mention that typography can convey dense and nuanced information but also has the danger to confuse and complicate [9]. They point out that words are primarily recognized by their shapes, and therefore, all capital

letters are to be avoided [9]. For better readability, the text-to-background contrast should be 80% [9]. Additionally, Cooper et al. (2014) suggest that a sans-serif font with a minimum size of 10 pixels is a good choice [9]. Tidwell et al. (2019) support this recommendation, arguing that sans-serif typefaces are more readable at smaller sizes and that 12 pt is the standard for body sizes [27].

Tharangie et al. (2010) conducted a study with the aim of improving effective color selection in designing human-machine interfaces [28]. The study aimed to confirm that the psychological aspect or the affective dimension of color plays an important role in interface design towards user satisfaction [28]. For this, a group of twenty adults from Sri Lanka, aged between 40 and 60 years were asked to map colors with appropriate Kansei words and provide reasons for these associations [9]. The results found that warm and cool colors generally induce pleasant and exciting feelings, while neutral colors like gray, brown, and black tend to induce unpleasant and unexciting feelings [28]. This led Tharangie et al. (2010) to the conclusion that designers should balance colors associated with negative effects with highly preferred colors to create a more appealing interface [28]. Cool colors such as green and blue are recommended for background and theme colors, while warm colors like red are better suited for highlighting when used sparingly to avoid overwhelming the user [28]. Although the chosen colors were carefully picked to be the least likely to be confused by different cultures [28], cultural differences still play a significant role in color perception [29], raising whether these results can be universally applied to all UI designs.

Cooper et al. (2014) point out that color is also a tool to draw attention [9]. Significant differences in value, hue, and saturation will draw the user's attention and should be used accordingly [9]. They urge designers to avoid the "carnival effect", which is a crowded palette of color and easily overwhelms users [9]. To avoid this, they recommend using a limited number of hues with not too much saturation. Tidwell et al. (2019) further imply that highly saturated colors evoke energy, vividness, and warmth but can tire the user's eyes and should be used sparingly [27]. Additionally, they warn against using complimentary colors, which are opposites in the color wheel, as this can also fatigue the user's eyes [27].

While the EU Commission's recommendations included providing the user feedback, Cooper et al. (2014) goes a step further and recommend using constant feedback, especially positive feedback, and to avoid negative audible feedback, such as for errors [9]. However, this approach might not be suitable for this thesis's use case. Constant feedback, even if positive, has the potential to distract the user from their primary task of driving safely from A to B. A more appropriate approach, similar to the recommendation of Tidwell et al. (2019), is to use feedback

when the user is waiting for an action to complete [27], like a server connection or reply. This way the user is reassured something is actually happening in response to a gesture [27], but otherwise they can focus on the road.

2.5 Conclusion

This literature review explored key areas for designing UIs for VRUs, particularly cyclists, interacting with human-machine interfaces. The review highlighted the EU Commission's recommendations emphasizing safety and minimized distraction as a focus for road user UI designs. This aligns with the broader finding that UI design should prioritize simplicity, minimal interaction requirements, and clear feedback mechanisms to avoid distracting users.

A significant gap identified is the reliance on simulated environments for research. There is a clear need for studies conducted in real-world traffic conditions to accurately assess UI effectiveness. While simplified UI elements and pictorial information foster trust and manageable workload, shifting some information to the periphery of human vision presents a promising avenue for exploration. Similarly, while voice commands hold potential for reducing cognitive load, since the workload seems to be not as high anyway, focus can be shifted to other areas in this thesis's final design.

The review also examined various sensory modalities for conveying information to the user. While auditory signals can enable faster reaction times, existing research often relies on external speakers or headphones, rendering an approach which solely focuses on auditory signals not suitable for this thesis. Additionally, no study explored positive auditory feedback, focusing solely on warnings, despite its potential benefits. This of course supports the idea that this approach might not be suited for UI design of cyclists for its potential to be distracting. This is an approach that needs further research. vibro-tactile feedback, though promising, primarily utilizes handlebar-mounted vibration motors, again presenting limitations for this use case. Visual modalities, while familiar and trusted by users, require supplementation from other modalities for optimal performance. A combination of visual and auditory feedback appears promising, leveraging the strengths of each modality to enhance reaction times, trust, and provide efficient driving instructions.

Several design principles emerged as crucial for effective UI design. Simplicity is the key, limiting the use of colors and graphics to avoid overwhelming the user. Well-established iconography, supplemented with text, can maximize user comprehension. Typography should prioritize readability through sans-serif fonts, a minimum size of 10pt, and high text-to-background contrast. When using iconography, it should be supplemented with additional text for maximum

Related work

comprehension. Color palettes should utilize cool colors for backgrounds, warm colors for highlights, and leverage hue, saturation, and value to draw attention without creating a distracting “carnival effect”. Finally, feedback should be strategically implemented to reassure users during waiting times or upon successful maneuver completion, minimizing distractions while driving.

This review underscores the need for further research into UI design for VRU interaction with automated vehicles, particularly in real-world settings. Future studies should explore the optimal balance of sensory modalities, the potential of peripheral vision displays and voice commands, and the development of effective feedback mechanisms that prioritize safety and minimize distraction.

3 Method

This chapter outlines the research methodology used in this thesis. Building on the insights from the literature review, the methodology is designed to evaluate and improve the UI for VRUs in dynamic traffic environments. The chapter is structured as follows: Section 3.1 outlines the prerequisites, section 3.2 details the development of the UI, and section 3.3 explains the validation methods used.

3.1 Prerequisites

This section outlines the prerequisites for the development and evaluation of the UI, including the full use case description, initial software, and baseline UI used for comparison.

The Android software used in this thesis was initially developed for a previous Nokia project, project LUKAS [30]. This software has been updated to incorporate the new PoDIUM project library connector and the updated MCM standard. As a result, the app is now ready to serve as a baseline for the UI design in this thesis. Most functionalities related to connections with the MEC server, as well as sending and receiving VAMs and MCMs, are already implemented. Additionally, the old UI from project LUKAS and later PoDIUM, which was used for initial testing, will be used as a baseline for comparison with the newly developed UI in this thesis. The initial concept and its shortcomings will be analyzed in 3.1.2.

3.1.1 Use case process and message flow

Scenario 2 of use case 1 involves a VRU approaching an intersection from the north, with a static road blockage in their way [2]. Simultaneously, on the other side of the road a CAV approaches from the south [2]. Both the VRU and the CAV are connected to the MEC server and detected by the infrastructure sensors [2]. The VRU aims to overtake the road blockage to continue their journey [2].

This scenario is divided into two phases [2].

Phase one: continuous computation of the environmental model

Phase one is the continuous computation of the environmental model, where the VRU sends their route, position, and velocity via VAMs to the MEC server [2]. The server also receives the object detection data of the infrastructure sensors, computes a digital twin and sends it to both

the VRU and CAV [2]. By combining the smartphone-based VAM data with infrastructure sensor detections, the system achieves improved VRU localization accuracy, helping to compensate for the inherent imprecision of smartphone GPS measurements [2].

Phase two: cooperative maneuver planning

As the VRU approaches the blockage, they request a cooperative maneuver using a MCM, which starts the second phase: cooperative maneuver planning [2]. The MEC server plans a cooperative maneuver and as soon as CAV has accepted to either slow down or come to a full stop, sends another MCM to the VRU with the “ConfirmationRequiredFlag=true” [2]. To continue the VRU needs to accept the maneuver by sending a MCM back with the “AdviceFollowed=true” [2]. Then the VRU receives periodic updates with the maneuver waypoints and maximum time to arrive at them via MCMs from the server [2]. During the maneuver execution, both the VRU and MEC server exchange periodic “keep-alive” signals via MCMs, allowing each party to monitor the other’s active participation in the cooperative maneuver [2]. After the VRU reaches their final waypoint and are safely maneuvered around the obstacle, all participating road users continue their journey [2].

During the second phase, the first phase continues so that the digital twin is kept updated with new data throughout the complete scenario [2]. The scenario is visualized in figure 2. The exchange of MCMs between the VRU and the MEC server is visualized in figure 3.

Figure 2: PoDIUM use case 1, scenario 2 visualization. Data source: [2]

Figure 3: PoDIUM use case 1, scenario 2 message flow diagram. Data source: [2]

For this thesis it is assumed that the correct network settings to connect to the MEC server and the desired path the user wants to travel are already set, so setting these will not be part of the final UI design.

3.1.2 PoDIUM cooperative awareness user interface concept

The PoDIUM project already has a “cooperative awareness human-machine interface concept” which lets users send and receive all necessary messages to test for use case 1, scenario 2 [2].

The following figure 4 shows the concept.

Figure 4: PoDIUM cooperative awareness human-machine interface concept [2].

This concept is already implemented in the Android software used for this thesis and consists of the following buttons and information panels:

- **Edge Server Connection:** This button establishes, cancels and monitors the connection of the VRU to the MEC server.
- **VAM Status:** This button activates and deactivates the creation and sending of continuous VAM messages to the MEC server.
- **Cooperation:** This button sends a cooperation request to the MEC server by sending an appropriate MCM.

- **Accept button:** This button accepts an incoming suggested cooperation from the MEC server. Not shown in figure 4 but implemented in the app.
- **Reject button:** This button rejects an incoming suggested cooperation from the MEC server. Not shown in figure 4 but implemented in the app.
- **Cooperation State:** This info panel displays all the relevant information regarding the current state of the cooperation.
- **Maneuver Information:** This info panel displays all the relevant information regarding the maneuver information like distance of calculated waypoints or remaining time to complete the maneuver.

While this concept is functionally effective, it provides extensive information regarding the coordination process. Cooper et al. (2014) describe this as one of the four reasons why digital products fail [9]. They argue that developers, when also charged with the design of the product, often focus on solving challenging technical problems and while their solutions are technically advanced, they are difficult to use and control [9]. However, as highlighted in the literature review, the final UI should prioritize simplicity and minimize interactions to avoid distracting the user while driving. The literature emphasizes the importance of presenting information that is quickly and easily understood with short glances, avoiding clutter, and using standardized icons and symbols [14] [26] [15].

This existing concept will serve as a baseline for comparison with the newly developed UI in this thesis. The goal is to measure whether the new UI improves upon the old one by enhancing usability and reducing user distraction, in line with best practices identified in chapter 2.

3.2 Development of the user interface

In *About Face: The Essentials of Interaction Design*, Cooper et al. (2014) fully introduce and describe a design process called “goal-directed design” [9]. The core premise of their book is that if a digital product is designed so that users can easily achieve their goals, they will be satisfied, effective, and happy [9]. They argue that most digital products fail because they don’t consider the user’s end goals and lack a design process [9]. To avoid these pitfalls, and given that the use case of this thesis has clear user goals, the “goal-directed design” methodology by Cooper et al. (2014) will be applied in the development of the UI for this thesis. Additionally, the insights and best practices from chapter 2 will be applied to the design.

The “goal-directed design process” involves the following steps:

- **Design research:** This step provides qualitative data about the behavior, attitudes, and aptitudes of potential product users [9]. The goal is to gain detailed knowledge of the user the product should be designed for [9].
- **Modeling:** User models or “personas” are synthesized using the behavioral patterns learned in the research [9]. These “personas” help the designer understand the user’s goals [9].
- **Scenarios and design requirements:** Scenarios, similarly to use cases, are used to imagine ideal user interactions and define the product’s behavior [9]. This includes not only the system’s functionalities, like in use cases, but the overall system’s behavior, including what functions the user sees and how they interact with them [9]. These scenarios are then used to extract the design requirements, which define what the product does before defining how it does those things [9].
- **Designing the product:** The actual design of the product, involves a definition of the interaction and visual design framework followed by the refinement of those frameworks [9].

Conducting full market research and modeling personas would be a huge endeavor, out of scope for this bachelor’s thesis. However, Cooper et al. (2014) also describe a literature review as a valid option to do design research [9]. With the insights learned from Chapter 2 and the description of PoDIUM’s use case 1, this thesis will apply the core principles of “goal-directed design” in a streamlined manner to identify the main user goals.

This leads to the following methodology for designing the UI:

- Synthesize key user goals from chapter 2 and PoDIUM’s use case 1, scenario 2 description.
- Create scenarios, based on PoDIUM’s use case 1, scenario 2 and expand upon them.
- Define the product requirements based on the scenarios.
- Define the interaction and visual design framework and refine them.

By focusing on leveraging existing research, defining high-level user goals and scenarios, and conducting iterative design and testing, the core principles of “goal-directed design” can be applied within the scope of this bachelor’s thesis. This approach allows for the creation of a user-centered UI within the constraints of time and resources available.

3.2.1 User goals

Based on Chapter 2 and scenario 2 of PoDIUM's use case 1, the following goals for a potential user have been synthesized:

- **Ensure safety:** The primary goal for the VRU is to navigate through the intersection safely. This involves avoiding collisions with other vehicles, especially the CAV, and managing any road blockages effectively. Safety is primarily enhanced through increased visibility achieved by communication mechanisms, specifically through VAMs and MCMs, which ensure continuous awareness of the VRUs presence and intentions.
- **Minimize distraction and maintain awareness:** The VRU needs to maintain focus on the road and stay aware of their surroundings, including the positions and intentions of other road users.
- **Enhance efficiency:** The VRU aims to continue their journey with minimal delays.

3.2.2 Scenarios

PoDIUM's use case 1, scenario 2 was already described in 3.1.1. This scenario will be taken as the basis for further scenario development, according to the "goal-directed design process".

Scenario 1: successful maneuver

The user is cycling to work on a typical weekday morning. As they approach a busy intersection, they notice a construction site blocking their side of the road. They glance at their phone mounted on the handlebars and check if they can send a cooperation request. The app clearly shows that the user is connected to the MEC server and can request the cooperation. The user presses the easily accessible button to request the cooperation and continues cycling.

After a short while, the app provides clear multimodal feedback indicating that the cooperation request was accepted and the cooperation has started. The app provides clear and concise instruction on how to overtake the road blockage and how much time the user has to do so. The instructions include a dynamically updated waypoint and time progress, ensuring the user knows exactly where to go and how long it will take.

The user follows the instruction, feeling confident and reassured by the timely and accurate information. The user arrives at the final waypoint safely and on time. The app provides clear feedback that the maneuver was a success. Relieved and satisfied, the user continues their journey normally.

Scenario 2: user cancellation

Scenario 2 starts the same way scenario 1 does, up until the point where the cooperation has started.

However, the user decides to switch to the pedestrian path instead. They press the easily accessible button to cancel the cooperation. The app provides immediate feedback confirming that the cooperation has been canceled. The user then switches to the pedestrian path and continues their journey, pushing their bicycle.

Feeling relieved by the app's responsiveness and clear communication, the user safely navigates the construction site on foot. They appreciate the flexibility and control the app provides, allowing them to adapt to changing circumstances. The user resumes their journey, confident in the app's ability to support their decisions.

Scenario 3: server cancellation

Scenario 3 starts the same way scenario 1 and 2 does, up until the point where the cooperation has started.

However, suddenly, the connection to the MEC server is lost. The app provides immediate feedback, notifying the user that an error has occurred, and the cooperation has been canceled. The user acknowledges the error message and assesses the situation. If the user is already in the process of overtaking the road blockage, they quickly and carefully finish the maneuver, relying on their judgment and the last received instructions. If the user has not yet started the overtaking maneuver, they stop at the road blockage and wait for reconnection to the server. The app periodically checks for a connection and informs the user with clear multimodal feedback of the status. Once the connection is re-established, the user can send a new cooperation request.

Feeling reassured by the app's immediate feedback and clear communication, the user appreciates the app's ability to handle unexpected situations. The user continues their journey, confident in the app's support and reliability.

3.2.3 Requirement definition

With the three scenarios in mind, the next step is to define the data, functional and contextual requirements of the UI.

Data requirements

- **Server status:** The user needs to know if they are connected to the MEC server. This information is crucial for determining whether they can request a cooperation. The app should provide clear and immediate feedback on the server connection status.
- **Cooperation status:** The user needs to know the current state of the cooperation. This includes:
 - Whether the cooperation request has been sent.
 - Whether the cooperation request has been accepted.
 - Whether the cooperation is in progress.
- **Maneuver information:** The user needs detailed maneuver information, including:
 - The distance to the next waypoint.
 - The direction to the next waypoint.
 - The progress of the maneuver.
 - The number of waypoints.
 - The maximum time allowed to reach the final waypoint.

Functional requirements

- **Request cooperation:** The user should be able to send a cooperation request to the MEC server.
- **Cancel cooperation:** The user should be able to cancel an ongoing cooperation and cooperation request.
- **Acknowledge errors:** The user should be able to acknowledge error notifications and take appropriate actions.

Contextual requirements

The most relevant information for the user is the maneuver information. All details regarding maneuvers need to be displayed with a primary focus, ensuring that users have all the necessary information to complete their maneuvers safely and efficiently.

The cooperation status and controls to request and cancel cooperations need to be grouped and displayed together. This ensures the user can easily assimilate all necessary information without having to navigate through different parts of the interface.

Since the server status is directly influencing whether the user can cooperate, it should be displayed together with the cooperation status. This provides users with immediate feedback on their ability to request cooperation, reducing uncertainty and improving decision-making.

3.2.4 Interaction framework definition

Step 1: Define form factor, posture, and input methods

The form factor for the product is a smartphone app. Given the limited screen real estate, it is important to strip the UI down to its essence, leaving only the most important functions on the front of the screen. Also, since the app will be used outdoors, the UI must be visible in both bright sunlight and dark conditions.

The basic posture of the app is transient, as it will be used while the user is engaged in a sovereign mechanical activity of riding a bicycle. This means that the app should minimize the need for detailed interaction and instead focus on providing quick and easy to understand information. Bold colors and high contrast can be used to ensure visibility in various lighting conditions.

A major takeaway from chapter 2 was to avoid cluttering the interface with too much information at the same time. For that reason, the UI will be split into two major screens: The “Pre-cooperation” screen and the “Active cooperation” screen. This way, all the textual displays can be combined into one and only be shown when the context is right. This ensures that the user always knows where to look for textual information. Additionally, buttons are only shown when they can be used or are needed, reducing unnecessary visual clutter.

The primary input method will be the touch screen, which is the most common interaction method for smartphone apps. A secondary input method could be voice command, but as chapter 2 showed, there is no immediate need to focus on voice commands. Touch input alone is sufficient for this use case.

Step 2: Define functional and data elements

As learned from chapter 2, it is not enough to focus on icons alone. Additional text will maximize user comprehension. That is why for each icon, there is also a textual representation planned.

Also, the use of animated graphics is minimized to only the Maneuver information indicator dynamically pointing in the direction the user should be heading to.

Cooper et al. (2014) recommend pretending the product is a polite, and considerate human assistant helping the user accomplish their goals [9]. For this reason, the connection and reconnection to the server should not be a task for the user but happen automatically in the background.

With those insights, the requirements from section 3.2.3 can be further improved upon to these functional and data elements:

- **Server Status:**
 - **Server status indicator:** A simple icon changing its appearance based on the server status.
 - **Server status display:** A text area that shows the current state of the server connection (e.g., “connected”, “disconnected”, “connecting”).
- **Cooperation management:**
 - **Request cooperation / Cancel request button:** A button labeled “Request cooperation” to send cooperation requests. The button switches to a cancellation button as soon as it is pressed once, and is then labeled “Cancel Request”.
 - **Cancel cooperation button:** A button labeled “Cancel Cooperation” to cancel an ongoing cooperation.
 - **Cooperation status display:** A text area that shows the current state of the cooperation (e.g., “Request sent”, “Request accepted”, “In Progress”).
- **Maneuver information:**
 - **Maneuver information indicator:** A simple arrow icon, dynamically updating and pointing in the direction of the next waypoint. The icon changes to a green check mark arrow when the maneuver is completed, or a red “x” when the maneuver was aborted for any reason.
 - **Maneuver information display:** A text area that shows the distance to the next waypoint (e.g., “Next waypoint in 12 m”, “Final waypoint in 15 m”).
 - **Waypoint progress bar:** A progress bar showing the progress of the maneuver and amount of waypoints in the maneuver.

- **Time progress bar:** A progress bar showing the maximum time allowed to reach the final waypoint and complete the maneuver.
- **Error handling:**
 - **Acknowledge error button:** A button labeled “Acknowledge” for the user to confirm they have seen the error message and understand the next steps.
 - **Error message display:** A text area showing the reason for the error or cancellation of the cooperation (e.g., “Server connection lost”, “Cooperation timeout”, “Unknown error”).

As all the textual information will be combined into one element, as described in 3.2.4, from now on the displays for “Cooperation status”, “Server status”, “Maneuver status”, and “Error message” will be collectively referred to as the “status display”.

Step 3: Determine functional groups and hierarchy

As determined in 3.2.4, the app will be split into two primary screens or “views”. The user always starts with the “Pre-Cooperation” screen and, as soon as the cooperation is in progress, automatically switches to the “Active cooperation” screen.

In the “Pre-cooperation” screen, the user only needs to know whether they are connected to the server, what the state of the cooperation is and be able to request and cancel the request for the cooperation. The “Server status indicator” and “status display” are the first things the user will check before requesting a cooperation. Therefore, they should be displayed together and at the top of the view. Since they aren’t too critical in relation, they don’t need too much screen space. Far more important is the ability to request cooperation. The “Request cooperation / Cancel request” button needs to be easily accessible while riding a bicycle, and it would be best if the user couldn’t even miss the button so they wouldn’t even have to look at the screen to hit it. Therefore, an almost screen filling button would be a good practice here. Additionally, the button can also imply the server status. If it is enabled and colored, the user knows they can press the button; therefore, they must be connected to the server. On the other hand, if it is disabled and greyed out, the user knows they aren’t connected right now. This would also help shift the information about the server connection to the user’s periphery, reducing the need to look at the screen and reducing distraction.

In the “Active cooperation” screen, the “Server status indicator” and “status display” are still at the same position with the same size. This way, the user always knows where to look if they quickly want to see the current state, now including maneuver and error information. Then, in

place of the “Request cooperation / Cancel request” button, right in the middle of the screen and quite large to draw the user’s attention, the indicator and both progress bars related to the maneuver information will be grouped together. With the biggest focus on the “Maneuver information indicator”, which should be the largest and right in the middle of the screen for best viewability and easy and quick understanding of where to drive. The progress bars for time and waypoints can then be around or next to the indicator. Finally, the least important element is the “Cancel cooperation” button. Since the user could also just cancel the cooperation by ignoring it, the button is not critical, but still giving the option to the user will be helpful. For that reason, the button will be smaller and placed at the bottom of the screen.

Step 4: Sketch the interaction framework

The next step is to roughly sketch the interface. Cooper et al. (2014) recommend keeping it simple at first and to iteratively try different ways of fitting elements together or visualizing them [9]. After nine iterations, the tenth and final iteration is visualized in figure 5.

Figure 5: 10th and final iteration of the interaction framework sketch. SSI = server status indicator

Step 5: Construct key path scenarios

The sketched interaction framework will now be applied to the main scenario, described in 3.2.2. Figures 6 to 11 visualize the scenario roughly.

1. The user is riding a bicycle with an Android smartphone mounted on it.

2. The device automatically connects to the MEC server and is ready to cooperate.

Figure 6: Storyboard part 1: Sketched interaction framework of the main scenario described in 3.2.2

3. A road blockage appears ahead of the user.

4. The user requests cooperation by pressing the 'Request Cooperation' button.

Figure 7: Storyboard part 2: Sketched interaction framework of the main scenario described in 3.2.2

5. The app indicates that the request has been sent and is now waiting for a response from the server.

6. The MEC server responds, and the app switches to the 'Active Cooperation' view, displaying all relevant maneuver information to the user.

Figure 8: Storyboard part 3: Sketched interaction framework of the main scenario described in 3.2.2

7. The user starts overtaking.

8. The time keeps counting down, and the waypoint progress fills up.

Figure 9: Storyboard part 4: Sketched interaction framework of the main scenario described in 3.2.2

9. The user overtakes the obstacle.

10. The user completes the maneuver.

Figure 10: Storyboard part 5: Sketched interaction framework of the main scenario described in 3.2.2

11. The app indicates that the maneuver was successful.

12. The app switches back to the 'Pre-Cooperation' view and is ready for another cooperation.

Figure 11: Storyboard part 6: Sketched interaction framework of the main scenario described in 3.2.2

Regarding feedback, the storyboard already shows when and what kind of visual feedback the user will receive. As chapter 2 showed, the best approach for this thesis will be a mix of visual and auditory feedback. But to limit the distraction, the combination of both modalities will only be used, when the app requires the immediate attention of the user or if it is important for the user to know their interaction was registered. A detailed overview of the feedback the user gets from the app is described in the following scenarios:

Scenario: Server changes status

- **User goal:** Monitor the connection status to the server.
- **User action:** None needed.
- **App response:**
 - 1. The “Server status indicator” changes its appearance to reflect the new connection status.
 - 2. The “Request cooperation / Cancel Request” button changes its appearance to reflect the new connection status.
 - 3. The “Status display” updates to show the connected state.

Scenario: Cooperation requested

- **User goal:** Initiate a cooperation.
- **User action:** The user clicks the “Request cooperation” button.
- **App response:**
 - 1. A subtle “click” sound plays to confirm the user’s action.
 - 2. The “Request cooperation” button changes its appearance to the “Cancel Request” button.
 - 3. The “Status display” updates to show “Cooperation requested”.

Scenario: Cooperation request canceled

- **User goal:** Cancel a pending cooperation request.
- **User action:** The user clicks the “Cancel Request” button.
- **App response:**
 - 1. A subtle “click” sound plays to confirm the user’s action.
 - 2. The “Cancel request” button is disabled and greyed out.
 - 3. The “Status display” confirms the cancellation.
 - 4. The UI switches back to its initial state.

Scenario: Cooperation starts

- **User goal:** Begin the cooperation.

- **User action:** None needed.
- **App response:**
 - 1. The app switches to the “Active cooperation” view.
 - 2. A positive chime composed of a four-note synth chord plays to notify the user.

Scenario: Cooperation in progress

- **User goal:** Monitor the progress of the cooperation.
- **User action:** The user is actively participating in the cooperation.
- **App response:**
 - 1. The “Maneuver information indicator” dynamically turns with the user and points at the next waypoint.
 - 2. The “Time progress bar” counts down from 100% to 0%.
 - 3. The “Waypoint progress bar” fills up from 0% to 100%.
 - 4. The “Status display” shows the distance to the next point and dynamically updates with the user’s progress.
 - 5. A short, positive chime consisting of a three-note synth chord plays when the user reaches a new waypoint.

Scenario: Cooperation ends successfully

- **User goal:** Complete the cooperation.
- **User action:** The user reaches the final waypoint.
- **App response:**
 - 1. The “Maneuver information indicator” changes to a green check mark to show the cooperation is complete.
 - 2. The “Status display” updates to show “Cooperation successful”.
 - 3. A longer, positive chime consisting of a three-note synth chord plays, to confirm the successful completion.

Scenario: Cooperation ends with user cancellation

- **User goal:** Cancel the cooperation.
- **User action:** The user clicks the “Cancel Cooperation” button.

- **App response:**
 - 1. A subtle “click” sound plays to confirm the user’s action.
 - 2. The “Maneuver information indicator” changes to a red “x” mark to show the cooperation is canceled.
 - 3. The “Status display” updates to show “Cooperation canceled”.

Scenario: Cooperation ends with an error

- **User goal:** Understand and resolve the error that occurred during the cooperation.
- **User action:** None needed.
- **App response:**
 - 1. The “Maneuver information indicator” changes to show an error icon.
 - 2. The “Status display” updates to show the error message.
 - 3. A short, neutral “beep” sound plays to alert the user.
 - 4. The “Cancel cooperation” button switches its appearance to the “Acknowledge error” button.

Scenario: User acknowledges error

- **User goal:** Acknowledge the error and return to the previous state.
- **User action:** The user clicks the “Acknowledge error” button.
- **App response:**
 - 1. A subtle “click” sound plays to confirm the user’s action.
 - 2. The “Status display” updates to show “Error acknowledged”.
 - 3. The app switches back to the “Pre-cooperation” view.

This way the user always receives rich modeless feedback in every state, as Cooper et al. (2014) recommend [9]. The “click” sounds for pushing buttons are already an Android standard and will be used as is to confirm successful button pushes. These familiar sounds provide immediate feedback to users, ensuring they know their actions have been registered. All the other sounds were carefully selected from <https://freesound.org/> to enhance the user experience without being too long, loud, or distracting.

Step 6: Check designs with validation scenarios

With the interaction's coherence and flow confirmed, the last step in defining the interaction framework is to check the design with validation scenarios [9]. Cooper et al. (2014) state that these scenarios usually don't need to be as detailed and developed as the key path scenarios [9]. Since the interactions for the alternative scenarios described in 3.2.2 are already mapped in 3.2.4, this concludes the definition of the interaction framework according to the "goal-directed design process".

3.2.5 Visual design framework definition

Step 1: Develop experience attributes

As Cooper et al. (2014) describe, the first step in defining the visual design framework is to choose a set of three to five descriptive keywords to help with tone definition of the design [9]. These adjectives have to fit the user's goals [9]. From the goals defined in 3.2.1 the following keywords will be used to help define the visual design of the UI:

- **Safe**
- **Reliable**
- **Efficient**

Step 2: Develop visual language studies

Cooper et al. (2014) recommend trying out between three and five different visual styles, with two extreme options, and presenting them to the stakeholders [9]. Since this is a bachelor's thesis and the only real stakeholder is the PoDIUM project, the most logical approach is to apply their visual design and brand guidelines to the UI.

The colors, defined by PoDIUM, include four different blue tones [31] which, as learned in chapter 2, is a recommended theme color and mixed with warmer colors will result in an exciting interface. However, since the final UI doesn't need to be exciting but rather "safe", "reliable", and "efficient", warmer colors will not be used. Instead, the blue tones will be combined with a green and a red tone indicating positive feedback (green) or negative feedback or an error (red). To avoid eye fatigue, as green and red are complementary colors, they will rarely be used at the same time or next to each other. For the best visibility and contrast, all colors will be displayed on a white background. A "dark mode" is not considered for this thesis for now.

All color contrasts were checked according to the recommendations of the “World Wide Web Consortium”[32] using the online color contrast checker tool from “Coolors” [33]. All colors used have at least the level AA (minimum contrast) of 4.5:1, with almost all of them having level AAA (enhanced contrast) of 7:1. Therefore, one of the blue tones from PoDIUM’s brand guidelines will not be used as it only has a contrast ratio to a white background of 4.2:1 [31][33].

The main colors chosen are shown in the table 1:

Table 1: Color palette. HSL = Hue, saturation, luminance.

Color	Hex Code	RGB Values	HSL Values	Contrast Ratio (White)	Usage
Text	#272e40	39, 46, 64	223, 24, 20	13.54:1	Text
Primary Blue	#451683	69, 22, 131	266, 71, 30	12.39:1	Buttons and elements with higher priority
Secondary Blue	#8E54E9	142, 84, 233	263, 77, 62	4.57:1	Buttons and elements with lower priority
Error Red	#AE1313	174, 19, 19	0, 80, 38	7.24:1	Errors and alerts
Success Green	#0D650B	13, 101, 11	119, 80, 22	7.28:1	Positive feedback
Background	#FFFFFF	255, 255, 255	0, 0, 100	-	Background

As for the visual style itself, PoDIUM project’s style aligns best with a flat design. Tidwell et al. (2019) describe flat design as using solid background colors, simple understandable icons, and sans serif typography [27]. This aligns with the best practices for UI design, as learned in chapter 2, and will therefore be applied for this thesis.

Font families used by PoDIUM are Google’s “Roboto” for printed media and Microsoft’s “Calibri” for digital media [31]. Since the app, developed for this thesis, is an Android app, using the “Roboto” font family will ensure design consistency and native compatibility.

Icons will be used from Google’s “Material Design 3” library [3] which Tidwell et al. (2019) also mention as an example for flat visual design [27]. As learned from chapter 2, using one visual style for icons and sticking with it is important for good design. Therefore, no other sources will be used for icons.

Step 3: Apply the chosen visual style to the screen archetype

In the final step, the defined visual style was applied to each functional element, defined in the interaction framework 3.2.4.

The buttons are categorized in primary, secondary, and disabled buttons using “Primary Blue”, “Secondary Blue”, and the Android’s standard grey tone for disabled buttons. Primary buttons have the highest contrast to the background and draw the most attention from the user. Secondary buttons have less important functions and therefore draw less attention with their color, while disabled buttons are to be ignored by the user for the time being.

- **Request cooperation button**

- **Button type:** Primary button / disabled button
- **Reason:** Requesting cooperation is the most important interaction the user has to perform to communicate with the MEC server. Once disconnected from the server, this action cannot be performed, and the button is disabled to quickly show the user they are disconnected.

- **Cancel request button**

- **Button type:** Secondary button / disabled button
- **Reason:** After requesting cooperation, the “Request cooperation button” turns into the “Cancel cooperation button”, keeping the same size and screen position. To show the user a change has occurred, the button switches color to “Secondary Blue”. Additionally, the function to cancel a cooperation request is less important to the user, as this is an edge case.

- **Cancel cooperation button**

- **Button type:** Secondary button / disabled button
- **Reason:** This function is also less important to the user, as they could let the cooperation time run out to achieve the same result. Therefore, this button is smaller and uses the “Secondary Blue” color. When the button is pressed, it becomes disabled so that the user can’t press it a second time by accident.

- **Acknowledge error button**

- **Button type:** Primary button

- **Reason:** Since the user doesn't want to miss the error message explaining why the cooperation was canceled, the app won't move on until they acknowledge the error. To highlight this importance, the button uses the "Primary Blue" color.

All buttons are visualized in figure 12.

Figure 12: Primary, secondary, and disabled buttons using flat design.

The progress indicators used were based on Google's "Material Design" [34]. Only the "Waypoint progress bar" was made with a modified version of Google's "CircularProgressIndicator"-class [35] to include the dynamic number of waypoints along the progress bar. For their unreached progress, the standard grey color was not changed to stay in line with the Material Design's design language.

- **Server status indicator**

- **Color:** Primary blue
- **Reason:** This state of the "Server status indicator" is only shown when the app is trying to connect to the server. To show the user that something is loading and the app didn't freeze, it uses the "Primary Blue" color. Additionally, during the unconnected state, the only other element that would use it and draw the user's attention would be the "Request cooperation button", but in its unconnected state, it is disabled and grey, shifting attention to the loading indicator.

- **Waypoint progress bar**
 - **Color:** Success green / Material Design 3 standard grey
 - **Reason:** The “Success Green” color gives the user a positive feeling of accomplishment each time they make progress driving and reaching waypoints.
- **Time progress bar**
 - **Color:** Secondary blue / Material Design 3 standard grey
 - **Reason:** The time left for the completion of the maneuver is mostly set long enough that it will never be an issue for the user. Therefore, the time is not as important as other information, and the “Secondary Blue” color is chosen to not draw too much attention to this element.

All progress indicators are visualized in figure 13.

Figure 13: Waypoint, time, and server status progress indicators in their different states.

The icons used from Google's "Material Design 3" library are the "Arrow Upward", "Check", "Exclamation", "Bigtop Updates", "Signal Disconnect", and "Close" [3]. All icons either use "Success green" or "Error red", depending on whether the feedback is positive or negative.

- **Server status indicator**

- **Icon used:** "Bigtop Updates" (connected) / "Signal Disconnect" (disconnected)
- **Color:** Success green (connected) / Error red (disconnected)
- **Reason:** As learned in chapter 2, it is best to use already learned iconography to make it easier for users to understand them. However, using a "Wi-Fi" icon or a "Mobile Data" icon could give the user the wrong impression that there is something wrong with the mobile connection of their phone, and that they have to take action to reconnect. Therefore, the "Bigtop Updates" and "Signal Disconnect" icons were chosen as they share some similarities with already learned icons like "Wi-Fi" icons (the signal waves) but without giving the user the wrong impression.

- **Maneuver information indicator**

- **Icon used:** "Arrow Upward" (Overtaking in progress) / "Check" (Maneuver complete / successful) / "Exclamation" (Maneuver canceled by error) / "Close" (Maneuver canceled by user)
- **Color:** Success green (Arrow and check) / Error red (Exclamation and close)
- **Reason:** This is the main information source for the user during cooperation. With one glance, they must be able to see whether everything is going according to plan or if something is wrong. Therefore, green and red were chosen as they are universally associated with positive and negative feedback. The arrow and check icons are very easy to understand. The arrow points where the user has to drive, and the check shows a completed maneuver, giving positive feedback to the user. The exclamation icon was chosen to differentiate a canceled maneuver by the user (with the "Close" icon) from a canceled maneuver due to an error. It draws more attention to the app in combination with the "Acknowledge error button" and prompts the user to see and understand the error shown in the "Status displayed" via text.

All icons used are visualized in figure 14.

Figure 14: Material Design 3 icons used [3].

Lastly, for the typography, all the text on the background uses the “Text” color, and all the text on the buttons uses the “Background” color for best readability. Important text uses 25 scale-independent pixels (sp), and less important text is in 18 sp. The importance of text coincides with the importance of the element it is displayed on. Therefore, the “Server status” display always shows important text. The same goes for the text on the big primary buttons “Request cooperation button”. The secondary button “Cancel request button” has the same font size to keep a consistent design. The smaller buttons “Cancel cooperation button” and “Acknowledge error button” use 18 sp as font size. Even though the importance of the latter is higher, since the former is there first, it is important to keep the same size and design for consistency. The font sizes and their differences are visualized in figure 15.

Primary Text 25sp

Secondary Text 18sp

Figure 15: “Roboto medium” in two font sizes (25 sp and 18 sp) used for this thesis.

3.3 Validation Method

This section outlines the methodology used to validate the new UI design compared to the old UI using the GOMS framework and the design grid quality check method.

3.3.1 Goals, operators, methods, and selection rules (GOMS)

The GOMS method is a framework to understand how users perform tasks by breaking them down into four components: goals, operators, methods, and selection rules [25].

- **Goals:** The objectives that users aim to achieve when interacting with the application. These can be broken down into sub-goals to represent more granular tasks [25].
- **Operators:** The basic actions that users can perform within the application, such as clicking a button, typing text, or moving the mouse. Each operator has an associated heuristic average time it takes to complete [25].
- **Methods:** The sequences of sub-goals and operators that users follow to accomplish their goals. Methods represent the procedures or strategies that users employ [25].
- **Selection Rules:** The guidelines or criteria that users follow to choose among different methods when multiple methods are available to achieve the same goal. These rules help in deciding the most appropriate method based on the context [25].

According to John and Kieras (1996), the GOMS framework has already been validated in various real-world scenarios, providing both qualitative and quantitative predictions of user performance [25]. However, they emphasize that GOMS has its limitations and is best used in combination with other validation methods and not by its own [25].

To compare the new UI with the old baseline UI, both will be modeled using the GOMS framework with the same user goal of scenario 1, described in 3.2.2. They will then be compared based on the task time required to complete the scenario, as shorter task times indicate more efficiency and therefore a better UI. System response times will not be considered, and it is assumed

that responses follow immediately. The scenario will be modeled with the “Cogulator” tool by the “MITRE cooperation” [36]. The results will be categorized into perceptual (look, hear, perceptual processor), cognitive (cognitive processor, ignore), and motor (point, touch) tasks. Each category’s time will be analyzed separately, as well as the total time, to facilitate comparison

Goals

The main goal in scenario 1 is to “Safely overtake a road blockage”. Using the Android application, this goal can be broken down into the following sub-goals:

- **Enable edge server connection:** The user enables the connection to the MEC server. In the new UI, this happens automatically.
- **Enable VAM sending:** The user starts sending VAMs to the MEC server. In the new UI, this happens automatically.
- **Verify connection:** The user checks whether they are connected to the MEC server.
- **Request cooperation:** The user requests cooperation.
- **Receive feedback and respond:** The user receives feedback from the MEC server and responds with appropriate actions.
- **Three cooperation information checks:** For the purposes of this validation test, it is assumed that the user checks the cooperation information three times: once at the start, mid-cooperation and after successful cooperation.
 - **Initial cooperation information check**
 - **Mid-cooperation information check**
 - **Successful cooperation check**

Operators

To achieve their goals, the user can use the following operators:

- **Look:** Look at an element at a known position. Time: 550 ms [36]
- **Point:** Point at an element at a known position. Time: 950 ms [36]
- **Touch:** Touch an element. Time: 490 ms [36]
- **Hear:** Listen to auditory feedback. Time: 400 ms [36]

- **Cognitive processor:** One cycle of cognitive information processing. Time: 70 ms [36]
- **Perceptual processor:** One cycle of perceptual information processing. Time: 100 ms [36]
- **Ignore:** Remove element from working memory. Time: 50 ms [36]

Methods

The following methods are shared by both the new and the old baseline UI:

- **Push a button:**
 - **Look** at button.
 - **Point** to button.
 - **Cognitive processor** verify button.
 - **Touch** button.
 - **Ignore** button.
- **Look at UI and verify information:**
 - **Look** at UI element.
 - **Perceptual processor** perceive UI element.
 - **Cognitive processor** verify information.
 - **Ignore** UI element.

When the cooperation is about to start in the baseline UI, there is no auditory feedback, and the user must manually accept the cooperation with a button push:

- **Receive feedback and respond:**
 - **Look** at “Cooperation state”.
 - **Perceptual processor** perceive “Cooperation state”.
 - **Cognitive processor** verify information.
 - **Ignore** “Cooperation state”.
 - **Look** at “accept” button.
 - **Point** to “accept” button.

- **Cognitive processor** verify “accept” button.
- **Touch** “accept” button.
- **Ignore** “accept” button.

In the new UI, the user also receives auditory feedback, and the cooperation is accepted automatically:

- **Receive feedback and respond:**
 - **Hear** “Cooperation start sound”.
 - **Perceptual processor** perceive silence.
 - **Look** at “status display”.
 - **Perceptual processor** perceive “status display”.
 - **Cognitive processor** verify information.
 - **Ignore** “status display”.

Selection rules

For the selection of methods, it is assumed that in this simple scenario, users always take the same action. It is also assumed that if the user has the choice to receive information from multiple sources, they will always first choose the known source (e.g., they could check the server connection via the “status display” or the “Server status indicator”).

Scenario sequence

In the old UI, the scenario sequence is assumed as:

- 1. Enable edge server connection
- 2. Enable VAM sending
- 3. Verify connection
- 4. Request cooperation
- 5. Receive feedback and respond
- 6. Initial cooperation information check
- 7. Mid-cooperation information check

- 8. Successful cooperation check

For the new UI, the scenario sequence is the following:

- 1. Verify connection
- 2. Request cooperation
- 3. Receive feedback and respond
- 4. Initial cooperation information check
- 5. Mid-cooperation information check
- 6. Successful cooperation check

The scenario could be modeled in more detail, but for the purposes of a quick comparison of both UIs, it was kept as simple as possible.

3.3.2 Design grid quality check

Franz and Kauer-Franz (2024) describe a quick way to quality check a UI, called the “Design grid” [16]. They argue that presenting a large amount of content in an appealing and clear way is a challenge, and their design grid helps designers to quickly and easily evaluate the quality of their design. The grid involves simply placing vertical and horizontal guides on the design and then checking the amount and different spaces.

For vertical lines, you draw a line on the left and right of each element and then count the number of lines. More vertical lines equal a choppy interface. For horizontal lines, a line is drawn on the top and bottom edges of all the elements, and you count the number of different distances between the lines. Fewer different distances equal a smoother image.

By applying the design grid method, the goal is to identify areas where the new UI has reduced visual clutter and improved alignment. This will help determine if the new UI provides a smoother and more appealing visual experience.

4 Results

4.1 Presentation of Data

This section presents all the final data and results gathered from conducting the thesis, without any assessment.

4.1.1 Final user interface design

The final design after, applying the insights from chapter 2 and using the “goal-directed design process” by Cooper et al. (2014) [9], is presented in figure 16 and 17.

Figure 16: Final UI design. All the states of the “Pre-cooperation view”.

Figure 17: Final UI design. All the states of the “Active cooperation view”.

The final design uses a flat visual design, with Google’s “Material Design” icons and elements, the “Roboto” font family, and colors from PoDIUMs brand guidelines. For user feedback, it uses mainly visual feedback, with selective instances of visual and auditory feedback.

The new and old UIs are visualized in the following figure 18.

Figure 18: PoDIUM project’s old baseline UI (left) next to the newly developed UI (right)

4.1.2 GOMS evaluation data

After comparing both the old baseline UI with the newly developed UI the resulting data was combined into table 2. Performance of each UI is visualized in Gantt charts in figure 20 and 19.

Table 2: Comparison of task time results for “scenario 1: successful cooperation” using the GOMS method.

Category	Old UI (ms)	New UI (ms)	Improvement (ms)	Improvement (%)
Perceptual	5450	4300	1150	21.1%
Cognitive	1080	720	360	33.33%
Motor	4810	1440	3370	70.06%
Total	11340	6460	4880	43.03%

Figure 19: Gantt chart of the old UIs performance in the GOMS evaluation.

Figure 20: Gantt chart of the new UIs performance in the GOMS evaluation.

4.1.3 Design grid quality check data

The data from applying the Design Grid method to all views of both the old and new UI is combined into table 3. The results can also be seen in figure 21 and 22.

Table 3: Design grid validation method data. Lower numbers equal a smoother and more appealing interface.

UI View	Vertical Lines	Difference	Horizontal Different Distances	Difference
Old UI	7	-	8	-
New UI: Pre Cooperation View	5	-2	4	-4
New UI: Active Cooperation View	9	+2	6	-2

Figure 21: Design grid validation method. Vertical lines on the old and new UI. More vertical lines equal a choppy interface.

Figure 22: Design grid validation method. Horizontal lines on the old and new UI. Each color represents a different distance between elements in one view. Less different distances equal a smoother image.

4.2 Analysis of results

This section will analyze the results and data from section 4.1.

After using the streamlined version of the “Goal-directed design” process, the final developed UI adheres to all the best practices and insights learned from chapter 2 and avoids any pitfalls the old UI had.

The GOMS evaluation demonstrated that the new UI significantly improves task efficiency. Users need 43.03% less time to complete the same tasks compared to the old UI. Notably, the new UI reduces the time spent on motor activities by 70.06%. This improvement is primarily due to the reduction in the number of button presses required, as the server connection, VAM sending, and acceptance of incoming cooperation are all handled automatically in the background without user intervention. Additionally, it should be noted that the evaluation did not include user response times. Since the new UI uses visual and auditory feedback to get the user’s attention, it can be assumed that the user would react faster to the system, which would improve the result of the new UI even more.

The design grid validation method, showed that compared to the old baseline UI, the new UI has a reduction of two vertical lines in the “Pre-cooperation view” and an increase of two vertical lines in “Active cooperation view”. Regarding horizontal different distances, the “Pre-cooperation view” has four fewer distances, and the “Active cooperation view” has two fewer distances compared to the old UI.

4.3 Interpretation

This section interprets the results in the context of the research questions and objectives, discussing whether the new UI meets the user goals and improves upon the baseline UI.

The new UI design achieves several key improvements:

- **Fewer interactions with the UI:** The reduction in the number of button presses and interactions simplifies the user experience, making it less distracting and easier to use.
- **Simpler visual design:** The use of fewer colors and a flat design avoids the “carnival effect”, resulting in a cleaner and more focused interface.
- **Enhanced efficiency:** The significant reduction in task completion time and motor activities demonstrates that the new UI is more efficient than the old UI.

-
- **Improved safety:** The reduction in motor activity time and the use of clear, concise information presentation help users maintain focus on the road, enhancing safety.

These results indicate that the new UI not only enhances efficiency but also improves the visual layout, making it less cluttered and more streamlined during the pre-cooperation phase. Although the active cooperation phase shows an increase in vertical lines, the overall reduction in horizontal distances suggests a more consistent and smoother interface. This balance between vertical and horizontal elements ensures that the interface remains functional and visually appealing across different phases of user interaction.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The new UI design meets the user goals and the objectives of the thesis by providing a safer, more efficient, and user-friendly interface for VRUs. The improvements in task efficiency, visual layout, and reduced distraction demonstrate that the new UI is a significant advancement over the baseline UI. Future work should continue to refine the UI through iterative testing and user feedback to ensure it remains effective and user-friendly.

Applying the results of this thesis can contribute one step to the EU's "Vision Zero" goal. By reducing the needed interactions of VRUs while still giving them the full capabilities to cooperate with other road users, they are more likely to safely navigate through traffic. Simplicity and low distraction are the key for UI design for traffic purposes. Designers must aim to strike the right balance between giving the user all the functionalities and information needed without overwhelming or distracting them from their primary purpose: safely navigating through traffic. Apps designed to help VRUs should always be seen as supplementary and not necessary to the user. If it doesn't help the user achieve their goal more easily and efficiently, then the app might even be counterproductive and defeat its purpose. In such cases, no one would use the app.

Since the final UI design was only evaluated using the GOMS and "Design grid" methodologies, further validation and user feedback is needed. Future work should include extensive user studies at the Ulm Lehr living lab, with a diverse group of participants and the use of actual CAVs to bring the test closer to reality. Testing more edge cases will help validate the suggested UI. Additionally, exploring different color schemes and developing a recommendation for a dark mode will enhance the UIs adaptability to various user preferences and conditions. More research is needed on the effectiveness and interpretation of the auditory feedback sounds used.

Expanding the design to cover the complete app and user experience, including setting the path and network configurations, will provide a more holistic approach to improving VRU interactions. The streamlined version of the "goal-directed design process" used in this thesis has proven effective in achieving the primary objectives. However, future studies should aim to implement the full version of the process to gain deeper insights and more comprehensive feedback. By continuously refining the UI through iterative testing and incorporating diverse user and stakeholder feedback, the design can be further optimized to meet the evolving needs of VRUs.

Discussion and Conclusion

Additionally, future studies should explore the optimal balance of sensory modalities, the potential of peripheral vision displays, and voice commands. Developing effective feedback mechanisms that prioritize safety and minimize distraction will further enhance the user experience.

In conclusion, the new UI design represents a significant step forward in enhancing the safety and efficiency of VRUs in dynamic traffic environments. By focusing on simplicity, low distraction, and user-centered design principles, this thesis contributes to the broader goal of achieving safer roads and supporting the EU's "Vision Zero" initiative.

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